

STUDENTS' ACADEMIC MOTIVATION AND LEARNING STRATEGIES DURING COLLABORATIVE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the academic motivation and learning strategies of Senior High School students during collaborative learning in the City of Koronadal for the Academic Year 2022–2023. A quantitative research design was employed, and data were collected from three hundred thirty (330) students from selected schools using a survey questionnaire adapted and modified by the researcher. The instrument was validated by experts to ensure its reliability and appropriateness. The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to describe the level of academic motivation and learning strategies and to examine the relationship between the variables. The findings revealed that the students are generally motivated in terms of their academic motivation and agreed that they utilize various learning strategies during collaborative learning. The results further indicated a significant relationship between academic motivation and learning strategies. Based on these findings, it was concluded that academic motivation plays a vital role in enhancing students' productivity, particularly in collaborative learning, as they apply appropriate strategies in different learning situations. It is recommended that students be provided with more opportunities to engage in collaborative activities, such as interactive classroom tasks and academic programs, to further develop their motivation and learning strategies.

Keywords: *academic motivation, strategies, collaborative learning*

INTRODUCTION

In today's educational landscape, collaborative learning has become a widely used approach for promoting active engagement, critical thinking, and meaningful interaction among students. It allows learners to work together toward shared goals, which enhances both academic achievement and social development (Folake, 2018). In this setting, students are not only expected to acquire knowledge but also to communicate effectively, cooperate with others, and think critically within group environments. Because of this, it is important to understand the different factors that influence students' participation and performance in collaborative learning.

One important factor is academic motivation, which serves as the driving force behind students' effort, persistence, and engagement in learning tasks (Pranitasari & Noersanti, 2017). Students who are motivated are more likely to show interest, maintain focus, and work toward achieving their academic goals. Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivations influence how learners behave and respond to learning activities (Silva, 2022). However, motivation is not fixed; it can change depending on the learning environment, teaching strategies, and individual differences among students (Abdulrahman, 2019). This makes it important to examine how motivation operates specifically within collaborative learning contexts.

Another key factor is the use of learning strategies. These strategies help students organize, understand, and apply information effectively, especially in group-based learning situations where interaction and shared responsibility are essential (Ortiz, 2020). Studies show that students who use appropriate learning strategies tend to perform better academically and become more independent learners (Mujib, 2019). In collaborative learning, strategies such as peer interaction, discussion, and cooperation play a major role in deepening understanding and improving performance (Johnson & Johnson, 1986).

Despite the existing literature, there is still a gap in research regarding how academic motivation and learning strategies are connected within collaborative learning environments. Many studies examine these variables separately, but only a few explore how they influence each other (Loes, 2022). This gap is particularly evident in local contexts, including Senior High School students, where limited studies have been conducted. Because of this, there is a need to investigate how motivation affects the way students use learning strategies during collaborative activities.

The topic is also timely due to the increasing shift toward student-centered and collaborative approaches in education. Schools are continuously adopting innovative teaching practices, but there is a need to ensure that students are both motivated and equipped with effective strategies to succeed in these environments. In the Philippine context, where collaborative learning is commonly practiced, understanding these factors can help address challenges such as low participation, lack of engagement, and ineffective group interaction among students.

Given these concerns, this study aims to explore the relationship between students' academic motivation and their learning strategies in collaborative learning. By focusing on Senior High School students in the City of Koronadal, this research seeks to address existing gaps and provide insights that may serve as a basis for improving instructional practices. Ultimately, the study offers a practical contribution by informing the development of interventions or strategies that can enhance students' motivation and strengthen their ability to learn effectively in collaborative settings.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the academic motivation and learning strategies of Senior High School students during collaborative learning in the City of Koronadal for the first semester of the Academic Year 2022–2023.

Specifically, this study sought the following:

1. To determine students' academic motivation in terms of;
 - 1.1. Amotivation
 - 1.2. External Regulation
 - 1.3. Introjected Regulation
 - 1.4. Identified Regulation
2. To determine students' learning strategies during collaborative learning; and
3. To determine the significant relationship between students' academic motivation and social learning strategies during collaborative learning.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in selected Senior High Schools in the City of Koronadal, South Cotabato. The respondents consisted of three hundred thirty (330) Senior High School students from both public and private schools, representing different academic strands. A simple random sampling technique, specifically the hat method, was employed to ensure that each student had an equal chance of being selected as a participant.

A quantitative descriptive-correlational research design was used to examine the relationship between students' academic motivation and learning strategies during collaborative learning. Data were collected using a survey questionnaire adapted and modified by the researcher.

The research instrument consisted of two parts. The first part measured academic motivation in terms of amotivation, external regulation, introjected regulation, and identified regulation, based on the Academic Motivation Scale (AMS) by Alivernini (2008). The second part assessed students' learning strategies during collaborative learning, adapted from the Co-regulated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (CRSLQ) by Olakanmi (2016). The questionnaire was composed of multiple items rated using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Very Low) to 5 (Very High). The instrument underwent

validation by expert validators to ensure its content validity and appropriateness. Revisions were made based on their suggestions prior to administration.

Data gathering was carried out by distributing the questionnaires to the selected respondents after securing necessary permissions from school authorities. The purpose of the study was explained to the participants, and their responses were treated with confidentiality and used solely for research purposes.

For data analysis, the mean was used to determine the level of students' academic motivation and learning strategies. Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was employed to examine the significant relationship between the two variables.

This study was limited to Senior High School students in selected schools in the City of Koronadal during the Academic Year 2022–2023. It focused only on academic motivation and learning strategies within collaborative learning contexts. The findings were based solely on self-reported data, which may be subject to response bias.

RESULTS

Table 1. Students' Academic Motivation

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTION
Amotivation		
1. Honestly, I don't know; I really feel that I am wasting my time in school.	1.90	Less Motivated
2. I once had good reasons for going to school; however, now I wonder whether I should continue.	2.03	Less Motivated
3. I can't see why I go to school and, frankly, I couldn't care less.	2.03	Less Motivated
4. I don't know; I can't understand what I am doing in school.	1.75	Not Motivated at all
5. For me, I think, going to school is a waste of time.	1.43	Not Motivated at all
Composite Mean	1.83	Less Motivated
External Regulation		
6. I go to school because I need at least a degree in order to find a high-paying job later on.	4.13	Motivated
7. I go to school in order to obtain a more prestigious job later on.	4.35	Highly Motivated
8. I go to school because I want to have "the good life" later on.	4.50	Highly Motivated
9. I go to school in order to have a better salary later on.	4.53	Highly Motivated
10. I go to school because I want a successful career later on.	4.63	Highly Motivated
Composite Mean	4.43	Highly Motivated
Identified Regulation		
11. I go to school to prove to myself that I am capable of completing my high-school degree.	4.28	Highly Motivated
12. I go to school because of the fact that when I succeed, I feel important.	4.25	Highly Motivated
13. I go to school to show myself that I am an intelligent person.	3.43	Motivated
14. I go to school because I want to show myself that I can succeed in my studies.	4.20	Motivated
15. I go to school to make myself feel that I can finish my studies.	4.25	Highly Motivated
Composite Mean	4.08	Motivated
Introjected Regulation		
16. I go to school because this will help me make a better choice about my career orientation.	4.20	Motivated

17. I go to school because it will enable me to enter the job market in a field that I like.	4.18	Motivated
18. I go to school because I think it will help me better prepare for the career I have chosen.	4.20	Motivated
19. I go to school because I believe that my education will improve my competence as a worker.	4.40	Highly Motivated
20. I go to school because I think this will help me become a successful person and succeed in my career.	4.38	Highly Motivated
Composite Mean	4.27	Highly Motivated
Grand Mean	3.65	Motivated

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Highly Motivated</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Motivated</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat Motivated</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Less Motivated</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Not motivated at All</i>

Table 1 shows the academic motivation of Senior High School students in the City of Koronadal for the first semester of the Academic Year 2022–2023 in terms of amotivation, external regulation, identified regulation, and introjected regulation. Furthermore, among the four given terms, the students are highly motivated in the external regulation as it got a composite mean score of 4.43 and the introjected regulation with a composite mean score of 4.27. The students are motivated in methods of research in terms of identified regulation which got a combined mean score of 4.08. At the same time, they are less motivated in amotivation as it got a composite mean score of 1.83.

Furthermore, it can be gleaned from Table 1 that the Senior High School students in the City of Koronadal for the first semester of the Academic Year 2022–2023 are motivated, as they obtained a grand mean score of 3.65.

Table 2. Students' Learning Strategies

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTION
When working in our group;		
1. I often remind others to contribute their ideas.	4.00	Agree
2. I make sure that everyone is participating.	4.38	Strongly Agree
3. I try to remind others of the time remaining to finish our work.	4.13	Agree
4. I make up questions to ask our group members to help find out whether we have understood the work.	3.88	Agree
5. I feel pleased if others remind me of the time remaining to finish our work.	4.13	Agree
6. I ask each of them their ideas and insights about our topic.	4.25	Strongly Agree
7. I ask for clarification if I do not understand something.	4.43	Strongly Agree
8. I ask myself questions to find out whether I've learnt what I want to learn.	4.08	Agree
9. I give feedback to contributions made by others.	3.83	Agree
10. I try to explain the task to others.	4.08	Agree
11. I ask others to explain concepts I don't understand well.	4.20	Agree
12. I try my very best to work with others to complete our task.	4.43	Strongly Agree
13. I help others who have difficulties in understanding the group task.	4.18	Agree
14. I am setting a goal to be accomplished.	4.18	Agree
15. I try to participate in the group discussions.	4.33	Strongly Agree

16. I work hard to do well even if I don't like what we are doing.	3.90	Agree
17. I often manage to keep on contributing my ideas until we finish the task even the topic is not interesting.	3.88	Agree
18. I am expecting for a better outcome after making our tasks.	4.18	Agree
19. I try to make sure we all make efforts to achieve our set goals.	4.28	Strongly Agree
20. I often think through our group's task and decide what I am supposed to learn from it.	4.15	Agree
Composite Mean	4.14	Agree

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat Agree</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>

Table 2 shows the learning strategies practiced by Senior High School students in the City of Koronadal for the first semester of the Academic Year 2022–2023. Furthermore, it shows that among the 20 indicated practices, the indicators that garnered the highest mean score of 4.43 state that the students strongly agree that they always ask for clarification if they do not understand something and always try their best to work with others to complete tasks. Aside from the above-stated indicator, students strongly agree that they continually practice the following strategies: making sure that everyone is participating (4.38), trying to participate in the group discussions (4.33), trying to make sure they all make efforts to achieve set goals (4.28), and lastly, asking others for ideas and insights about the topic (4.25).

Furthermore, it can be gleaned from Table 2 that the Senior High School students in the City of Koronadal for the first semester of the Academic Year 2022–2023 agree that they often practice different learning strategies, as indicated by a composite mean score of 4.14.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between the Students' Academic Motivation and Learning Strategies During Collaborative Learning

Variables	R Computed	P-Value	Decision at 0.05 Significance Level	Description
Motivation and Strategies	0.341296	0.010265	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship

Table 3 presents the relationship between the students' academic motivation and learning strategies during collaborative learning for the School Year 2022–2023. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyze the data. The results revealed that the students' academic motivation is significantly related to their learning strategies during collaborative learning.

Table 3 shows the computed correlation coefficient, where the null hypothesis was rejected at the 0.05 level of significance. The computed r-value of 0.341296 is associated with a p-value of 0.010265, which is less than the 0.05 significance level. This indicates that there is a significant relationship between the two variables.

DISCUSSION

The findings in Table 1 indicate that students generally possess a favorable level of academic motivation, as reflected by the grand mean of 3.65. The high levels of external regulation and introjected regulation suggest that students are significantly influenced by external rewards, expectations, and internal pressures such as the desire to meet standards and avoid failure. Meanwhile, the moderate level of identified regulation shows that some students are beginning to internalize the value of learning, although this is not yet fully developed. The low level of amotivation further implies that most students do not feel disengaged or indifferent toward their academic tasks. This pattern suggests that while students are motivated, their motivation is still largely influenced by external and controlled factors rather than purely intrinsic interest. These results are consistent with Pranitasari and Noersanti (2017), who emphasized that motivation is a key driver of student engagement. Likewise, the low level of amotivation supports the findings of Yusuf et al. (2022), indicating that students who recognize the connection between effort and outcomes tend to demonstrate higher levels of motivation. Thus, the results confirm that motivation remains a strong contributing factor in students' participation in learning activities.

The results presented in Table 2 show that students frequently use learning strategies during collaborative learning, as evidenced by the high composite mean of 4.14. This indicates that learners actively engage in interaction, cooperation, and shared problem-solving when working with peers. Such behaviors reflect the development of strategic and self-regulated learning skills within a collaborative setting. These findings align with Mujib (2019), who noted that the use of appropriate learning strategies contributes to improved academic performance and learner autonomy. In addition, the results are consistent with Johnson and Johnson (1986), who highlighted that collaborative learning environments promote deeper understanding through active participation and social interaction. The consistency of these findings suggests that when students are placed in collaborative contexts, they naturally adopt strategies that enhance both individual and group learning outcomes.

Table 3 reveals a significant relationship between academic motivation and learning strategies during collaborative learning. This indicates that students with higher levels of motivation are more likely to utilize effective learning strategies. In other words, motivation appears to influence how students approach and manage their learning processes. This finding supports the study of Loes (2022), which established that collaborative learning is associated with positive outcomes such as increased motivation and engagement. Similarly, Saeed and Zyngier (2012) found that motivated students tend to participate more actively and apply strategies that support their learning. The consistency of these results with previous studies strengthens the claim that motivation and learning strategies are interconnected variables that mutually reinforce each other in educational settings.

Overall, the results of the study demonstrate that academic motivation and learning strategies are closely linked within collaborative learning environments. The findings

consistently align with existing literature, confirming that motivated students are more likely to engage in strategic and meaningful learning practices. This implies that improving students' motivation can lead to better use of learning strategies, which in turn enhances their overall learning experience. Therefore, educators should focus on designing learning environments that not only encourage collaboration but also strengthen students' motivation and strategic learning skills to promote more effective and meaningful learning.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Students are academically motivated by the external factors in which they learn and go to school to have a greener pasture in life later on. External motivations such as having a high-paying job and a successful career are some of the motivations that students carry throughout their years in school. Some factors students can use in academic motivation are somewhat garnered low ideals in applying it to their studies.
2. Students acknowledge every student in doing tasks during collaborative learning. Students are aware of asking others to contribute their ideas within the collaboration. Likewise, they are giving their best in working with others to complete the assigned work.
3. The student's academic motivation and learning strategies during collaborative learning are correlated. This conclusion implies that highly motivated students perform better academically. Therefore, the result was an alternative hypothesis.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, teachers may apply collaborative learning strategies that enhance students' academic motivation and encourage the use of effective learning strategies. Schools may also provide programs and activities that support student engagement and motivation.

For future research, it is recommended to use larger samples or different groups of respondents to validate the findings. Researchers may also explore other variables or use different research approaches to gain deeper insights into students' motivation and learning strategies during collaborative learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured full compliance with ethical standards throughout the conduct of this study. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, and they were clearly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any penalty or consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly protected, and all information collected was handled in accordance with applicable Data Privacy regulations. The well-being of the participants

was safeguarded at all times, and the study was conducted in a manner that avoided any form of harm, discomfort, or coercion. The researcher declares that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of this study. All sources of information were properly cited, and plagiarism was strictly avoided. The interpretation of the data and findings was carried out objectively and without bias.

Furthermore, the results of the study were used solely for academic and research purposes. The researcher also discloses that Artificial Intelligence (AI) and digital tool were used to support the writing process, specifically ChatGPT for grammar refinement and Grammarly for plagiarism checking. However, all ideas, analyses, and interpretations remain the sole responsibility of the researcher.

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